

BLADE BATTERY TECHNOLOGY IN ELECTRIC VEHICLES: THERMAL CHALLENGES, DEGRADATION MECHANISMS, AND MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES

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Abstract: Lithium-ion batteries have become a crucial factor in the widespread adoption of electric vehicles, thanks to their high energy density and seamless integration with powertrain systems. However, their performance is highly dependent on operating temperature, necessitating an efficient thermal management system to ensure optimal efficiency, safety, cost-effectiveness, and longevity, particularly in high-capacity Li-ion batteries. This review provides a comprehensive analysis of heat generation mechanisms and thermal modeling in lithium-ion batteries, along with various thermal management systems. It examines the impact of extreme conditions on battery performance, including thermal runaway and aging. Ultimately, it aims to establish a comprehensive framework for future research and development in battery thermal management systems.

Keywords: Electric vehicles, degradation, thermal condition, blade battery.

I. Introduction

As battery prices fall and battery technology itself improves, the world is taking note and preparing for the electric vehicle revolution. Nearly all the major car manufacturers have thriving electric vehicle practices. The state of California in the US, along with the US federal government, is in fact offering substantial financial incentives to consumers purchasing electric vehicles [1]. So, on a year-on-year basis, the share of electric vehicle sales, as a percentage of overall vehicles sales, has been on the rise and this is a positive sign. As battery manufacturing capacity ramps-up around the world, as the who's who in car manufacturing begin to take a notice, as governments catalyze the adoption of electric vehicles and as consumers become aware of the environmental benefits, this share will continue to rise only further from here on out [2]. There were over 10 million EVs sold worldwide in 2022, and the market is expected to grow to 228 million by 2030 as a result of tight regulations in many countries [3]. Developing electrochemical batteries for transportation applications have begun in the 1990s with lead acid batteries and nickel metal hydride batteries (NiMH), while these efforts led to the exploitation of the Nickel Sodium Chloride as a new electrical energy storage option. As a result of their high energy and power density, EV manufacturers started using Li-ion batteries for energy storage in 2010 [4]. In recent years, a variety of Li-ion chemistry has been offered under the way of material development for expected application. Lithium cobalt oxide (LCO) is a good-performing battery with a high energy density, but it is

often used in small-scale applications due to its low thermal stability and still high price tag. The NiCd and NiMH batteries are the upcoming deployed LIBs due to their high-power density and affordable cost. Currently, batteries with a power density greater than 350 Wh/kg use lithium manganese oxide (LMO), lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC), lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide (NCA), and lithium iron phosphate (LFP) as electrode materials. There is a downside with LIB due to their sensitivity to the operating temperature, hindering its way for faster market uptake. The accumulation of generated heat during the charging and discharging process due to electrochemical process, especially in high-capacity batteries that are more appealing for EV manufacturers may cause thermal runaway and degradation of battery performance and even pose a threat to the safety of passengers [5]. According to the usage of protocols 15–35°C is optimal for the operation of LIB. NiCd and NiMH batteries are recommended for operation at temperatures between 20 and 32°C and – 20 to 45°C, respectively [6]. Temperature deviation inside battery pack which directly affects the battery electrical behavior is suggested to be maintained lower than 5°C to prevent uneven electrical characteristic [7]. Operating the battery at low temperatures can also possess adverse effects, such as capacity loss and degradation of active materials, due to decreased electrochemical reaction rates [8]. To support the widespread adoption of electric vehicles in various environmental conditions and to meet the demand for lifetime, longer mileage and proper performance, an effective and economical battery thermal management system is necessary to ensure suitable battery pack conditions. The battery thermal management system cools down the Li-ion battery pack when the temperature rises over the allowed range and warms up the battery pack when the environmental temperature is too low. Additionally, battery thermal management system ensures a uniform distribution of temperatures among battery packs to prevent uneven voltage of battery cells. Over the past few decades, various studies have focused on the battery thermal management systems, which plays a critical role in electric vehicle powertrains.

II. Blade Battery technologies in electric vehicle

Due to the lack of fuel and the severity of pollution, various manufacturers have launched their own pure electric models, and the use of batteries is particularly critical. Many new power manufacturers have no ability to produce batteries and can only use second-party batteries. At present, lead-acid batteries, nickel-metal hydride batteries and lithium-ion batteries are widely used [9]. But the problem of a spontaneous combustion caused by battery temperature control and battery energy consumption remains to be solved. It is the massive burning of fossil fuels that leads to energy shortage and air pollution that makes electric vehicles slowly come to the stage. The emergence of electric vehicles is to solve these problems, but the problem of batteries was not taken into account in the early stage. Although the emergence of blade batteries cannot completely solve these problems, it can greatly improve the original problems. This reviewed article specifically focused on the battery and thermal conditions of domestic new energy manufacturers, the principles of new energy manufacturers and BYD blade batteries, and the degradation behavior of blade batteries in electric vehicles under severe thermal condition.

Picture 1: The Blade battery structure of BYD

The Blade Battery, a type of lithium iron phosphate (LFP) battery, differs from conventional LFP batteries primarily in its elongated, thin design. The driving range of an electric vehicle is directly determined by the capacity of its power battery. The endurance mileage of electric vehicles is actually the endurance capacity of power batteries for electric vehicles. Simple analysis from top to bottom, the first level: if you want to improve the endurance of the same car with the same weight, you need to increase the battery capacity. level 2: improve battery capacity from two perspectives: one is to stack battery modules, the other is to improve energy density. The former brings an increase in weight and a discount in endurance, so improving energy density is the key. The third level: the key to improving energy density lies in the selection and proportion of cell materials, the optimization of the layout of battery internal space and the whole package space, and the "slimming" of the weight of the whole module or pack. The blade battery is to make the cell into a blade shape. The cell adopts laminated structure + ceramic coating technology. Through structural innovation, the "module" can be skipped in the group, that is, more batteries can be placed in the unit space. The blade battery is a sublimation of lithium iron phosphate. From the second law of improving energy density, the layout of the internal space and the whole package space of the battery is optimized [10].

III. Degradation behavior of blade batteries in electric vehicles under severe thermal condition.

Thermal management: The Blade Battery incorporates an integrated thermal management system to dissipate heat effectively. By placing the battery cells in direct contact with a thermally conductive material, the Blade Battery can maintain a stable operating temperature, preventing overheating and reducing the risk of thermal issues [11]. In traditional lithium-ion batteries, heat dissipation can be a challenge, leading to thermal buildup and potential performance degradation [12]. Battery degradation in electric vehicles is influenced by various factors, including user behavior and environmental conditions. The daily driving distance of an electric vehicles affects the depth of discharge, which plays a key role in battery wear. Driving speed and acceleration determine the discharge current, impacting battery performance over time. Among environmental factors, temperature has the most significant effect on battery aging, influencing both efficiency and long-term durability.

Picture 2: The influence in battery degradation from common factors in driving test.

The standby state takes up a considerable amount of time in electric vehicles' real-life operation, and the contribution to total aging is significant. The pace of the degradation process during standby, known as calendar aging, varies depending on the SOC and temperature. It is evident that the battery capacity fade is more notable at high temperatures than at a moderate temperature. In addition, high state of charges will also accelerate capacity fade due to the high voltage. As expected, the highest capacity degradation occurs in the toughest conditions, with a high storage state of charge (80%), and the highest temperatures (45°C) among these cases. Exposure to high temperatures, such as 45°C (113°F), can more than double the rate of capacity loss compared to standard conditions (25°C or 77°F). For instance, after 200 charge cycles, a battery at 45°C may lose approximately 6.7% of its capacity, whereas at 25°C, the loss is around 3.3%. This accelerated degradation is due to the growth of the solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer and lithium plating, which reduce the battery's effective capacity [13].

Charging speed, measured in C-rates, is another critical factor in battery degradation. The C-rate indicates how quickly a battery is charged relative to its capacity. Higher C-rates lead to increased stress on the battery's internal components, accelerating degradation, especially when coupled with high temperatures and it is showed on picture 3.

Picture 3: Battery temperature and Remaining Battery Capacity at different charge cycles.

Experimental studies on the thermal runaway (TR) of lithium-ion batteries have shown low repeatability and involve certain risks, requiring significant human and material resources. Furthermore, these studies are economically inefficient as they only provide limited observations of surface phenomena during the experimental process. In order to overcome these limitations, researchers have turned to numerical simulation software to simulate the thermal runaway process of lithium-ion batteries. The failure rate is estimated to be 1 in 40 million if LIB are stored and operated within the conditions recommended by manufacturers [14]. However, unforeseen circumstances such as overcharging, external heating and poor mechanical handling can significantly increase this failure probability. Although various safety devices have been integrated into commercial LIB packs, failures have occurred in many cells used in various fields, leading to accidents [15].

V. Conclusion

The widespread adoption of electric vehicles hinges significantly on the performance and reliability of lithium-ion batteries. Among various battery technologies, the Blade Battery, a lithium iron phosphate (LFP)-based system, stands out due to its structural innovations that enhance energy density, improve safety, and streamline thermal management. However, like all Li-ion batteries, Blade Batteries are susceptible to degradation, particularly under severe thermal conditions, which can negatively affect efficiency, longevity, and operational safety. This review has examined key factors influencing battery degradation, including heat generation, charging speeds, environmental conditions, and depth of discharge. High temperatures, especially above 40°C, were found to accelerate battery aging by promoting solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer growth and lithium plating, leading to capacity fade. Similarly, excessive charging rates (high C-rates) increase internal stress, reducing the lifespan of battery cells. The integration of advanced thermal management systems is, therefore, essential to regulate battery temperatures and mitigate degradation risks. The Blade Battery's unique design, which eliminates traditional module structures and optimizes

internal space, enables higher energy density while enhancing heat dissipation. This structural innovation allows for a more compact and efficient battery pack, reducing unnecessary weight and improving the overall performance of electric vehicles. However, while Blade Batteries offer significant advantages in endurance and safety, they still require robust thermal management strategies to prevent degradation, particularly in extreme environmental conditions. As electric vehicle adoption continues to grow globally, further research is necessary to refine battery thermal management techniques and develop enhanced materials that offer greater thermal stability. Additionally, improvements in battery manufacturing, predictive maintenance, and charging infrastructure will play a crucial role in ensuring the long-term reliability and sustainability of electric vehicle battery systems. Future studies should also explore the integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques for real-time battery monitoring and predictive analytics, helping to optimize battery life and prevent premature failure. Ultimately, the findings in this review underscore the importance of designing electric vehicle batteries that balance high energy efficiency with durability and safety, ensuring sustainable advancements in the transportation sector.

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